

METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM FOR IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING INFORMATION COMPETENCES OF FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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Abstract. *To analyze the role of information technologies in understanding historical processes, to develop the skills of analyzing and researching innovative approaches to the main directions of science, to explain the role of science in analyzing the factors of development of the state and society, to teach future history teachers to use electronic resources and Internet capabilities to develop information competence in teaching history, to use information in historical research consists of teaching the use of technologies, models and methods.*

Keywords: *models, methods, global informatization, Innovation, digital technology, digitization, types of activities, pedagogy, skills, IT technology.*

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 29, 2005 “On the Organization of the Public Educational Information Network of the Republic of Uzbekistan” [1], information resources on education and youth created by various structures of Uzbekistan in information transmission networks were combined into a single “ZiyoNet” information network. The main tasks of the network are: to form and develop national information resources for youth, to ensure wide use of information that contributes to the spiritual and intellectual development of young people, to promote a healthy lifestyle and popularize physical education and sports, to assist in the introduction of distance learning methods and other information and communication services for students and youth into the education system.

In creating an environment that ensures the active work with information of future history teachers, it is necessary to pay attention to ensuring the continuity of teaching (between subjects and within the subject), individualizing teaching, and creating conditions for the independent assimilation of educational material from information sources.

When analyzing the current state of development of information literacy competencies of students of higher education institutions, the subject program “Innovations in History: Technologies, Models and Methods” for students of the direction 5120300 – History (World Countries) was analyzed [2].

The process of developing the information competences of future history teachers based on the discipline “Innovations in History: Technologies, Models and Methods” is conditioned by the following:

- developing the activity of future history teachers in working with information;
- basing their communicative and innovative skills on working with information;
- developing the personal and professional preparation of future history teachers to use historical sources in working with information.

The tasks of teaching the subject are to analyze the role of information technologies in understanding historical processes, to develop the skills of analyzing and researching innovative

approaches to the main directions of the subject, to explain the role of the subject in analyzing the factors of development of the state and society, to teach students to use electronic sources of history, Internet resources, and to use them in historical research. consists of teaching the use of information technologies, models and methods.

The following requirements are imposed on the development of information competence of a future history teacher:

- the place of innovations in the field of history, historical research;
- he must know the general capabilities of modern information technologies, the advantages of using them in the field of history;
- search, process and analyze historical information and sources using information technologies;
- must have the skills to study electronic information based on scientific, historical, and objective methods;
- be able to use models and methods;
- independently acquire new knowledge, organize their activities on a scientific basis and be able to work on the process of working with modern information;

In the study of N.V.Morgacheva, when determining the structure of the methodological competence of a future science teacher, we observed four components:

- 1) the personal component includes motives, values, volitional motives and attitude to professional activity;
- 2) the cognitive-informational component includes knowledge of a subject, methodological and technological nature;
- 3) the operational and technological component includes knowledge of methods, methods and technologies of teaching natural sciences, skills of a methodological nature;
- 4) the activity component includes experience of methodological activity in the subject, experience of teaching natural sciences. [3]

Pedagogical and information technologies cannot be separated from each other, since the widespread introduction of modern pedagogical technologies changes the paradigm of education, and only the informatization of educational processes creates the opportunity for the effective use of pedagogical technologies [5].

In the context of innovative education, the informatization of future history education processes will lead to an improvement in the content and essence of education. A comparison of the main indicators of pedagogical education in the environment of traditional and modern information technologies clearly demonstrates the promising nature of informationized pedagogical education. This can also be confirmed on the basis of the following considerations. In traditional history education, didactics sets itself the goal of developing a teaching theory aimed at creating methodological methods aimed at optimizing the process of mastering knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of studying historical events.

The discipline "Innovations in History: Technologies, Models and Methods" is based on computer technology. The field of study of the discipline "Innovations in History: Technologies, Models and Methods" [2]:

- problems of using information technologies in historical research, special software, creation of historical databases and banks;

- use of information technologies in the analysis of given information and structuring, textual, visual and other sources;
- computer modeling of historical processes;
- use of information networks;
- use of new directions of multimedia and informatization, as well as information technologies in historical education.

In the first decade of the development of international scientific societies in the field of "Innovations in Historical Science: Technologies, Models and Methods", a clear structure of this professional community has been formed. This community consists of several closely interconnected groups and layers. They have different positions in the development of the discipline "Innovations in History: Technologies, Models and Methods" and contribute to this process [2]. The first group is future history teachers - those who are interested in developing new methods of presenting and analyzing historical source information, appropriate algorithms, programs and technologies. It was precisely the existence of this group that made it possible to recognize the discipline "Innovations in Historical Science: Technologies, Models and Methods" as a field of science with its own subject of study, special methods and research tools.

The second group of future history teachers are those who use new information technologies, methods and software, who master rapidly developing information technologies and apply the achievements of development to historical research.

The third and most numerous layer is the broad public of future history teachers with information literacy, who will use the results of the activities of the first and second groups in practice.

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